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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHAT SHE CHOSE: A TALE OF DREAMS AND DUTY”

She dreamed of heights with stars in hand,
A world beyond her small town's land.
Books her ladder, hope her guiding light,
She worked long into the night.

But poverty clung like winter's cold,
A heavy hand, a silent hold.
She bore a child before her time,
A lullaby, a mountain climb.

The cradle rocked with quiet cries,
While dreams grew dust under her eyes.
Yet still she moved, painfully slow,
With fire inside she never let show.

“I love you more than words can say,
But I won't ask you not to stay.
On roads you've shed for, hard and long,
Even if it means you walk alone, but strong”.

She kissed his lips with silent agony,
Chose dreams and child, not love's sweet ecstasy.
He departed weeping and turned away,
She stayed for what must never say.

Every night she stands alone,
A mother made flesh and stone.
Still chasing dreams, still bearing weight,
Still waling proud, though love must wait.